

CREATING AN ELECTRONIC RESOURCE FOR 6TH GRADE MATH USING MACROMEDIA FLASH

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Annotation. This article discusses the use of electronic resources in the teaching of mathematics and its educational value.

Keywords: Macromedia Flash, electronic resource, Layer, button, Text Tool, action, educational value.

Another e-resource for teachers, I created an e-textbook for 6th graders using Macromedia Flash to help them use math in class.

Macromedia Flash is a program based on the use of vector graphics in the format ShockWaveFlash (SWF). The flexibility of Flash and the ability to create interactive multimedia applications make it very convenient for us to create e-textbooks for use in the classroom. Flash is a program developed by Macromedia, such as Dreamweaver and similar programs.

Macromedia Flash has a number of ways to work with animations, create interactive elements in the interface, create Flash videos and, most importantly, create interesting videos and games for use during the lesson. The main Flash window consists of 4 main areas: menus, tools, object properties and add-ons, and workspace. The program menu consists of 10 sections.

Using this program, I created an electronic textbook of mathematics. Of course, each picture is posted in the appendix.

The general structure of Macromedia Flash is as follows:

On the left side of this program is a toolbar, which contains a variety of necessary tools. The long line at the top places all our work, which means that in the Layer layer we do all our work. My e-textbook looks like this:

All text was typed using the Text Tool (A) and the Start Button was created using the F8 key on the keyboard. Of course, once the button is created, some command will be added to it. The following command should be written in the Action section of this button.

```
on (release)
{
gotoAndStop (5);
}
```

In this case, the task of the operator gotoAndStop (5) is to provide the transition to the fifth frame. In the fifth frame, press F7 to create a new sheet. The

new page contains chapter topics. The above command is included in each topic, but the number of frames in parentheses must be changed.

There are also different games for each theme. Math games, of course, are not without calculations. The Flash program also has functions for mathematical calculations. They are in the math section and there are many, but all we need is simple actions. First of all, let's go to the game frame and write the assignment. Task a, b, c Find the largest of the variables. The following is written in the Action section behind the frame: : Var a,b,c;

```

    If (a > b & a > c) {q = a}; / * if a is greater than b and c, assimilate q to a *
*
    If (b > a & b > c) {q = b}; / * if b is greater than b and c, learn q to b * /
    If (c > b & c > a) {q = c}; / * if c is greater than c and c, assimilate q to c * /
    Trace ('largest number' + q);

```

The prepared game allows the student to find the largest of the 3 numbers using the code above.

The educational value of the use of electronic resources. The created electronic resource prevents the student from getting bored quickly during the lesson and increases his interest in science. For teachers, this e-resource teaches modern teaching and the use of information technology. In today's world of digital technology, teachers teach our younger generation how to use computers and their software properly. In today's world of digital technology everyone should know how to use computers and their software properly. This means that the duty of modern teachers is to install a love and interest for the science of IT. To do this, modern teachers must constantly find ways to draw students' attention to the subject. There are all possibilities for this in our country.

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